

Anonymised

Surname:

Anonymised

Name:

ID / Passport:

Duration: 1 hour 45 minutes

Room and time: C7100, 5 p.m.

Test: 50 points

Short questions: 10 points

Problem: 40 points

Test. 50 points

hit: + 2 points; **failure:** - 1 point; **no answer:** 0 points.

Please, answer in table, page 5

1. The cost of implementing a quality management system in an organization is:
 - a. Appraisal cost
 - b. Prevention cost.
 - c. Internal cost

2. Check a cost NOT produced by internal errors:
 - a. Cost from increasing quality
 - b. Cost from redesigning the product.
 - c. Cost from performing tests again.

3. Costs of non-quality are:
 - a. Produced by organizational internal errors
 - b. Coming from the organization trying to avoid that customers get faulty products
 - c. Costs from faults (faulty units)

4. The cost of training in quality in an organization is:
 - a. Internal error cost
 - b. Prevention cost
 - c. Appraisal cost.

5. A prevention cost can be:
 - a. Administrative checks when materials arrive.
 - b. Cost from implementing FMEA.
 - c. Repeating a job.

6. Controllable costs are:
- Appraisal costs.
 - Internal errors costs
 - Appraisal and prevention costs.
7. Within a business, a cost is good when it comes from trying to restore the customer confidence
- True False
8. Quality management principles according to the ISO 9000 family are:
- Customer focus, effective leadership, evidence-based decision making
 - Two others are true
 - (Supplier) relationships, Engagement of people, Improvement.
9. ISO 9000 standards family are a set of international standards and quality guides:
- Management and governance of the organization information systems.
 - The creation of a quality management system.
 - The organization processes improvement
10. A total quality management model:
- A set of recommendations to the organization performance assessment
 - A set of practices to help the total quality concepts work
 - A certifiable model that applies a set of standards.
11. ISO 9001
- Establishes base lines for continuous improvement and global efficiency.
 - Provides recommendations for improving quality management systems.
 - Defines requirements to specify a quality management system, and that can be used for certification.
12. Operational processes in a Process Quality Management System are related to management.
- True False
13. Strategic processes in a Process Quality Management System are related to management.
- True False
14. A process in a Process Quality Management System is:
- A document that describes the set of activities to perform
 - The organization structure required to implement a task management.
 - A set of inter-related activities.

15. A procedure in a Process Quality Management System is:
- Document(s) describing / specifying processes
 - The organization structure required to implement the quality management.
 - A set of inter-related activities that provide customers with added value and satisfaction
16. Standards are important because:
- They are very important for organizations because they certify the organization has a certain level
 - They define the extent quality criteria must be fulfilled and offer a set of best practices.
 - They are always certifiable, and the organization gets accredited in a certain area.
17. ISO 9000 family philosophy is based on:
- Improvement cycles and process based approach.
 - Information Systems improvement
 - Services and processes improvement.
18. The product quality model (ISO/IEC 25010) in the ISO/IEC 25000 family (SQUARE) includes the following attributes:
- Reliability, security, portability
 - Speed, performance, skill
 - Portability, reliability and incompatibility
19. The ISO/IEC 25000 family (SQUARE) provides a guide to plan and manage software evaluations
- True False
20. A software quality assurance plan includes activities aimed at evaluating the conformity of life cycle processes and software projects, since the conformity of the software product is the object of quality control.
- True False
21. A software quality assurance plan defines, among others (check the most precise bullet):
- A set of activities to assure that software processes comply with requirements, standards and procedures
 - A set of activities to assure that software products comply with requirements, standards, and procedures
 - A set of systematic and planned activities to assure that processes and their outputs comply with requirements, standards and procedures

22. In CMMI, a key process area is defined as:
- A set of objectives to increase the organization processes capability.
 - A set of indicators that proves an organization capability.
 - A set of practices that, when implemented, satisfies a set of goals
23. Key process areas, in CMMI, can belong to more than one maturity level.
- True False
24. CMMI is structured into maturity levels that contain:
- Key process areas.
 - Key practices.
 - Common characteristics.
25. The purpose of the IEEE 730 (IEEE Standard for Software Quality Assurance Processes) is:
- To establish a minimum, uniform and acceptable set of requirements, for a project software quality assurance (SQA) processes.
 - To determine a set of activities that assure that products, services and software components comply with a minimum set of quality requirements
 - Maintain processes within the established technical limits and reduce their variability.

Test responses

1.	
2.	
3.	
4.	
5.	
6.	
7.	
8.	
9.	
10.	
11.	
12.	
13.	

14.	
15.	
16.	
17.	
18.	
19.	
20.	
21.	
22.	
23.	
24.	
25.	

Short Questions. 10 points

1. What is a quality model in the context of the ISO/IEC 25000, SQUARE?
2. Indicate standards aligned or related to IEEE 730 (IEEE Standard for Software Quality Assurance Processes) (you can use the standard number or the name of the standards):
3. Please indicate how and why Quality Assurance and Quality Control are different?
4. Indicate three clauses / items of the ACM Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct that you consider relevant

Anonymised

Surname:

Anonymised

Name:

ID / Passport:

Problem. 40 points

- A. It is requested to define the scope, the owner and the clients of the process, and indicators, of the process described below **[15 points]**
- B. Design the diagram of the previous process, **using BPMN**, that models it by identifying its actors and the input and output documents that are generated by it **[25 points]**

In an IoT sensor sales company, the ordering process is carried out by two departments: the sales department and the warehousing department.

The order received by the warehousing department is checked against the stock. This operation is performed automatically by the warehouse department application, which consults the warehouse database. If the product is in stock, the central register/file is updated, and also a list is updated for strategic material orders, and retrieved from the warehouse before the sales department confirms the order. Sales then issues an invoice and waits for payment, while the product is shipped from the warehouse. The process is completed with the filing of the order in the sales department. If the product is not in stock, the application of the storage department checks the availability of raw materials by accessing the supplier catalogue, and if it is one of the strategic products, urgently it is necessary to manage the lack of the product, since this lack means that one of the system consistency mechanisms has failed. That would make it necessary to communicate it to the sales departments. Once the raw materials are obtained, the manufacturing department is in charge of manufacturing the product using a 3D printer. The process is completed with the purchase confirmation filed by the sales department.